

SOFT SKILLS MATEMATIS MAHASISWA CALON GURU MATEMATIKA

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Abstrak

Penelitian bertujuan untuk mengetahui *soft skills* matematis mahasiswa calon guru matematika yang meliputi kebiasaan berpikir cerdas, keaktifan, minat, motivasi, resiliensi matematik, konsep diri, kepercayaan diri, kemampuan diri, dan penghargaan diri. Populasi penelitian sebanyak 112 orang. Sampel penelitian sebanyak 30 orang yang dipilih dengan *purposive sampling*. Alat pengumpulan data menggunakan angket. Teknik analisis data menggunakan analisis deskriptif. Hasil penelitian menunjukkan bahwa *soft skills* matematis mahasiswa pada kategori baik dengan rincian: konsep diri pada kategori sangat baik; kebiasaan berpikir cerdas, keaktifan, minat, motivasi, serta kepercayaan diri mahasiswa pada kategori baik; serta resiliensi matematik, kemampuan diri, dan penghargaan diri mahasiswa pada kategori cukup.

Kata Kunci: *soft skills* matematis, mahasiswa calon guru matematika, analisis deskriptif.

Abstract

This research aimed to determine the mathematical soft skills of the student mathematics teacher candidates which include habits of mind, activeness, interests, motivation, mathematical resilience, self-concept, self-confidence, self-efficacy, and self-esteem. The population was 112 people. The sample was 30 people selected by purposive sampling. The data collection tool used a questionnaire. The data analysis technique used descriptive analysis. The results showed that the students' mathematical soft skills were in a good category with details: self-concept in the very good category; smart thinking habits, activeness, interest, motivation, and self-confidence of students in the good category; and mathematical resilience, self-ability, and self-esteem of students in the sufficient category.

Keywords: *mathematical soft skills, the student mathematics teacher candidates, descriptive analysis.*